

Climate change and its diverse regional impacts on Greenland's marine biota

Thomas Gjerluff Ager^{a,*}, Mikael K. Sejr^{a,d}, Carlos M. Duarte^b, Kenneth D. Mankoff^{e,f}, Vibe Schourup-Kristensen^c, David Boertmann^c, Eva Friis Møller^c, Jakob Thyrring^{a,d}, Dorte Krause-Jensen^{a,d}

^a Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, 8000 Aarhus C, Denmark

^b Biological and Environmental Science and Engineering Division, King Abdullah University of Science and Technology, Thuwal, Saudi Arabia

^c Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

^d Arctic Research Centre, Aarhus University, Denmark

^e NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies, New York, NY 10025, USA

^f Autonomic Integra LLC, New York, NY 10025, USA

HIGHLIGHTS

- Cumulative environmental change across Greenland's marine ecosystems.
- West, East, and Southeast Greenland are hot spots of environmental change
- Biota responses reflect the spatial variations in cumulative environmental changes
- 77 % of identified marine biota time series showed significant changes.
- Key knowledge gaps include impacts of multiple drivers and lower trophic level data

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This study quantified climate-driven changes and spatial variability in key environmental drivers over four decades along Greenland's coastal and shelf marine ecosystems and evaluated their impacts on marine biota divided into six regions. We analyzed trends in sea ice concentration and seasonality, sea surface temperatures, salinity, and freshwater inputs from ice discharge and freshwater runoff. West, East, and Southeast Greenland were most impacted by climate change, driven by increasing sea surface temperatures ($0.22\text{--}0.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C decade}^{-1}$), freshwater inputs ($10.14\text{--}24.93\text{ Gt yr}^{-1}\text{ decade}^{-1}$), declining sea ice concentrations ($3\text{--}5.3\text{ \% decade}^{-1}$), and more open water days ($10.92\text{--}23.9\text{ days decade}^{-1}$). The Northwest and Northeast regions appeared more resilient due to lower sea surface temperature increases ($0.01\text{--}0.03\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C decade}^{-1}$) and sea ice declines ($0.5\text{--}2.1\text{ \% decade}^{-1}$). Changes in Southwest Greenland were limited to sea surface temperature ($0.27\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C decade}^{-1}$) and freshwater runoff ($7.66\text{ Gt yr}^{-1}\text{ decade}^{-1}$) increases since the 1990s. Synthesized evidence from 94 marine biota time series showed 73 exhibiting significant changes, and 37 identified an environmental driver: sea ice (20),

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: tga@ecos.au.dk (T.G. Ager).

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temperature (19), and runoff (2). Only four time series considered multiple drivers. Biota time series trends mirrored regional environmental changes; 78 % changed significantly in West, East and Southeast regions combined, 73 % in southwest, and 56 % in the northern regions. Fish, benthic flora, and benthic fauna responses remained unclear due to data gaps, underscoring the need for further research. In conclusion, our findings reveal widespread biological change linked to climate but with distinct regional patterns in environmental drivers and associated responses across Greenland.

1. Introduction

The Arctic is the planet's most rapidly warming region, impacting ice extent, freshwater runoff, and ocean chemistry (Ahmed et al., 2020; Beer et al., 2020; Nielsen et al., 2022; Rantanen et al., 2022; Terhaar et al., 2020). These changes influence ecosystems and species, ranging from microbes to marine mammals (Wassman et al., 2011). One of the most pronounced changes in the marine Arctic is the loss of sea ice. The extent of summer sea ice has declined by about 12 % per decade since the late 1970s; a trend expected to continue to result in an Arctic largely free of sea ice in summer (Kumar et al., 2020). Concurrently, organisms depending on sea ice are challenged by the reduction in their habitat (Boye et al., 2020; Ehrlich et al., 2020; Post, 2017). Meanwhile, an earlier onset of sea ice melting in spring and delayed freeze-up in autumn also increases the Arctic open water period (Markus et al., 2009) and the productive season and net primary production in the water column (Arrigo and van Dijken, 2015). The reduction in sea ice enable poleward migration of boreal species, increasing interspecific competition and alter predation dynamics (Dupont et al., 2024; Goldsmit et al., 2020; Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2023; Rokicki, 2009), while also allowing for more light to reach the seafloor, thereby creating new habitats for primary producers such as macroalgae, benthic microalgae and eelgrass (Kahru et al., 2016; Krause-Jensen et al., 2012). The decline in sea ice cover thereby influences key ecological processes, including primary production and food webs (Dezutter et al., 2019) and affects ecological functioning by altering carbon and nutrient cycling (Kahru et al., 2016; Kortsch et al., 2015; Post, 2017). Increased ocean temperatures also impact marine ectotherms by affecting metabolic rates (Brown et al., 2004; Thyrring et al., 2017). In coastal areas, increased freshwater inputs from land affects stratification, light availability, and carbon and nutrient inputs (Ahmed et al., 2020). This has cascading effects on productivity and benthic vegetation patterns (Bartsch et al., 2016), and may increase some marine species' susceptibility to warming (Nielsen et al., 2021). Higher riverine discharge, coastal erosion, and increased wave-induced resuspension of sediments in coastal areas may counteract increases in light availability caused by the reduction in sea ice in coastal areas (Bartsch et al., 2016; Bonsell and Dunton, 2018; Sahade et al., 2015; Sejr et al., 2024). Arctic organisms are thus exposed to a mosaic of environmental drivers changing at different rates and showing different spatial dynamics (Box et al., 2019). These changes ultimately lead to changes in the diversity, composition, and structure of biological assemblages (IPCC, 2022). Although our understanding of changes in Arctic marine ecosystems in response to climate change is growing, some regions remain poorly studied, and quantitative measures of the impact of multiple interacting drivers are limited, especially for coastal ecosystems (Solan et al., 2020).

Greenland covers 24° of latitude and its coastline spans >44,000 km. The coastal and shelf ecosystems consist of a wide range of marine habitats supporting multiple functions and services regionally (e.g., fisheries, hunting, and tourism) (Meire et al., 2017) and globally (e.g., biodiversity and CO₂ sink capacity) relevant (Meire et al., 2015). Yet, information on marine ecosystems' response to climate change around Greenland remains limited. Spatial variations in environmental drivers of Greenland marine ecosystems occur both along the latitudinal and longitudinal axes. On a latitudinal scale, sea ice is present most of the year in the cold north, whereas it is largely absent in the southwest regions (García-Soto et al., 2021), so ecosystem responses to changes in

sea ice cover are expected to differ profoundly along Greenland's coastline (Lannuzel et al., 2020; Post, 2017). The Greenland marine ecosystems are also strongly linked to ocean currents. Cold, low salinity, nutrient-poor waters originating from the Arctic Ocean are transported south along the east coast of Greenland by the East Greenland Current (Gjelstrup et al., 2022). Further south, this current merges with the Irminger Current, which supplies warmer Atlantic waters characterized by higher salinities and nutrient contents, to form the West Greenland Current. The West Greenland Current carries the two water masses north along west Greenland, with the cold and fresh Arctic water at the surface and the Atlantic water at intermediate depths (Rudels and Carmack, 2022; Rysgaard et al., 2020). These current systems add an extra dimension to the spatial heterogeneity of environmental drivers. Moreover, warming drives the ablation of the Greenland Ice Sheet, with a subsequent increase in freshwater runoff and ice discharge to Greenland fjords (Mankoff et al., 2021; Mousavi et al., 2021). The inputs vary across regions with the highest ablation occurring in south and west Greenland, resulting in fjord scale differences in freshwater inputs contribute to the range of climate-related drivers of change in coastal and marine ecosystems (Holding et al., 2019; Meire et al., 2017). In fjords with marine-terminating glaciers, freshwater is introduced below the glacial foot generating upwelling of nutrient rich deep waters that can sustain primary production. Land-terminating glaciers, on the other hand, introduce freshwater with high sediment loads near the surface, resulting in increased stratification and turbidity, thereby reducing primary production (Holding et al., 2019; Meire et al., 2017; Oksman et al., 2022). This multi-scale variability in settings suggests major differences in climate trends and associated ecosystem responses across Greenland marine ecosystems.

Here we quantify the rate of change in key environmental drivers of biota change over four decades based on modelled and satellite information and compare changes across six regions covering Greenland's coastal and shelf marine ecosystems. The targeted environmental drivers are sea ice concentration, sea ice seasonality, sea surface temperatures, salinity, and freshwater inputs from solid ice discharge and liquid runoff. Existing knowledge on ecosystem changes and their impacts on Greenland biota Greenland is compiled with the aim to compare changes across regions, identify hot spots for change, investigate whether trends in biota correspond to changes in the environmental drivers, and to pinpoint knowledge gaps. We hypothesized that the trends of environmental drivers vary regionally, and that these differences are reflected in biota responses.

2. Method

2.1. Environmental drivers

The coastal ocean around Greenland was divided into six regions: Northwest (NW), Northeast (NE), West (W), East (E), Southwest (SW), and Southeast (SE). Each region spans 9 degrees latitude (58–67°N, 67–76°N, 76–85°N) and Western and Eastern regions are divided at 45°W. Regions extend 200 km off the coastline (Fig. 1). Previous regionalization based on climate factors exist (e.g. (Cappelen et al., 2021)), but a latitudinal subdivision of similar size was chosen to facilitate a more even comparison of biological studies across the regions. This approach allows for a balanced comparison of environmental factors and biological data, facilitating a more comprehensive analysis

Fig. 1. The six regions of Greenland used in this study: Northwest (NW), Northeast (NE), West (W), East (E), Southwest (SW), and Southeast (SE) Greenland.

of regional patterns across Greenland. Environmental drivers included: Sea ice concentration (1979–2021), sea ice seasonality (1979–2021), sea surface temperature (1979–2021), salinity (1991–2021), liquid (1979–2020) and solid ice (1986–2020) runoff from the Greenland icesheet. The data sets were obtained from satellite and modelled information and are specified below.

2.2. Statistics

For each environmental driver, we computed mean values, standard deviation (std), linear trends including 95 % confidence intervals using Sen's estimator of slope (Sen, 1968), and trend significance using a Mann-Kendall Trend Test (Kendall, 1948; Mann, 1945). We computed all four parameters for both individual pixels of data products and regional annual averages. To identify regions experiencing the greatest change in environmental drivers, and thus where biota may be exposed to the most pronounced environmental shifts, we standardized time series data by calculating z-scores. The z-scores express the deviation of each data point from the mean, measured in units of standard deviation. This standardization allowed for the comparison of changes across different environmental drivers, regardless of their original units and scales (Abramowitz and Stegun, 1970). However, it is important to note that z-scores do not directly reflect the impact on marine biota, but rather the relative strength of change in each environmental driver. We standardized data for sea ice concentration, sea ice seasonality, sea surface

temperature, salinity, and both liquid and solid runoff. For each of the environmental drivers, we first calculated the yearly z-scores for each region. These were then used to compute the trend in z-scores. This trend indicates whether a variable is becoming more extreme (moving further from the historical mean) or remaining stable (staying close to the mean). Finally, to quantify the accumulated change across all drivers, we summed the absolute values of the significant z-score slopes for each region to assess the overall magnitude of potential environmental change, ensuring that all drivers contribute equally, regardless of whether they exhibit positive or negative trends. Aggregating z-scores enables comparison without prescribing hierarchy or importance of the various components. This method provides a means to compare the relative strength of change across regions and environmental drivers, though it does not imply a causal relationship between the drivers and marine biota.

2.3. Biota response

We did a targeted literature review to identify peer-reviewed studies and scientific reports of time series in Greenland marine biota and communities in the following six categories: Benthic fauna, benthic flora, plankton (phytoplankton, zooplankton), fish, seabirds, and marine mammals within the six defined regions. Studies of plankton were obtained by a literature search in Web of Science using the criteria: (*plankton) AND (change OR variation OR time series) AND (marine OR ocean OR coastal) AND Greenland. Studies of benthic fauna, marine mammals and fish were obtained by a literature search in Web of Science using the criteria: (benth*), (marine mammal* OR pinniped* OR cetacea*) and (fish* OR pisces OR ichtyo*) respectively. Each of the three search strings were combined with AND (change OR variation OR time series) AND (marine OR ocean OR coastal) AND Greenland. The obtained studies were subsequently evaluated manually for relevance. For benthic flora, we used the findings of a recent pan-Arctic survey (Krause-Jensen et al., 2020). The review of seabirds was based on extensive personal expertise and familiarity with the relevant literature, drawing from a comprehensive understanding of the field. We limited time series by the following requirements: They extended into the 21st century and spanned >10 years of observations, represented by at least a start and an end observation. For each relevant time series, we noted the location, time period, number of observations per time, time points, frequency, and response in biota (a) behavior and phenology, b) growth and condition, c) abundance and demography, d) range shift, e) regime shift and community changes), and the rate of change if possible. This resulted in a total of 94 relevant time series. In a few cases, multiple responses were quantified, and therefore the number of responses is larger than the number of time series. Additionally, some time series encompassed data across multiple regions, resulting in an increase in the count of regional time series for all affected areas. In addition to the literature search, we analyzed trends in chlorophyll *a* concentration estimated from satellite imagery.

3. Data

3.1. Sea ice concentration

Sea ice concentration is the relative area of ice versus visible water within each pixel. Sea ice concentration is most widely used to determine sea ice extent, which is often quantified based on pixels with sea ice concentration of >15 % (Cavalieri et al., 1996). We used sea ice concentration data from the NOAA/NSIDC Climate Data Record of Passive Microwave Sea Ice Concentration v4. (<https://nsidc.org/data/g02202/versions/4>, accessed on 17th of January 2023 (Meier et al., 2021)). The data set provides daily, and monthly passive-microwave-derived sea ice concentration based on two well-established algorithms: the NASA Team algorithm (Cavalieri et al., 1984) and NASA Bootstrap algorithm (Comiso, 1986) to produce a more robust estimate

than individual algorithms. The passive-microwave data are gridded onto a polar stereographic projection with a grid cell resolution of approximately 25×25 km. We downloaded the monthly data from 1979 to 2021, which was compiled into a single NetCDF file. Using this file, we calculated the annual sea ice concentration for each year and for each quarter per year; Spring (March, April, and May), summer (June, July, and August), autumn (September, October, and November), and winter (December, January, and February).

3.2. Sea ice seasonality

Data on sea ice seasonality was downloaded from the NASA earth science webpage (<https://earth.gsfc.nasa.gov/cryo/data/arctic-sea-ice-melt>, accessed on 17th of January 2023) in its original grid format. To align it with our study regions, we reprojected the dataset onto a longitude-latitude grid provided by the National Snow and Ice Data Center (NSIDC). The dataset consists of four parameters of sea ice seasonality described using ‘day of year’: Early melt (earliest observed melt conditions), melt (melt conditions observed from this point until freeze), early freeze (earliest observed freeze conditions), and freeze (freeze conditions observed from this point on). The different parameters are based on the passive-microwave dataset, as described previously, and have been determined as described by (Markus et al., 2009). We downloaded data from 1979 to 2021. Given the nature of the algorithm, the earliest melt possible is day 75, and any values before this were filtered out. We then calculated the open water period by subtracting the melt date from the freeze date of each pixel for their respective years. In pixels where sea ice melting and freezing are not a yearly occurrence, a year-round ice cover or open water period will result in pixels with no values. Consequently, we computed two versions of the four parameters (std, mean, trend, and significance) for all three sea ice seasonality parameters:

- 1) The trends and average of pixels with recorded sea ice data
- 2) The trends and average, where pixels with ‘Not a number (NaN)’ values have been filled manually with a predefined value.

To calculate 1), we computed the parameters using the raw sea ice seasonality data. To ensure sufficient data points for statistical analysis, we only applied calculations when 10 or more years were available for a single pixel. To calculate 2), we identified areas with year-round sea ice (NW & NE regions) and assigned: Freeze date = 0, Melt date = 365, Open water period = 0. Similarly, for areas with year-round open water (E, W, SE, and SW regions), we assigned: Freeze date = 365, Melt date = 0, Open water period = 365. These adjustments had the smallest impact in the northern regions, where NaN-value pixels represent a minor fraction, while the number of no-value pixels increases towards south (Table 1). In both cases the analysis created pixels with large trends (>30 days). These high value pixels were colorized as 30 days when producing figures, so smaller trends are not diminished visually. For 1), 31 of 1411 pixels were set to 30, and for 2), the corresponding numbers were 163 pixels of 2340. In both cases, these pixels were in the Qeqertarsuup Tunua (Region W) and along the drift ice edge (Region E). The data set with filled values is presented in the results section and the raw data is presented in the supplementary materials.

3.3. Sea surface temperature

Sea surface temperature data was downloaded from the ERA5

reanalysis data set using the Copernicus Climate store (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/climate-reanalysis>, accessed 1/18/2023, (Hersbach et al., 2020)). The ERA5 is a recent reanalysis product provided by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasting (ECMWF). Reanalysis forces observational data through a physical model generating a globally complete and consistent dataset. The spatial resolution is $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$, and data is available in hourly time steps from 1959 to present. We used data from 1979 to 2021 to align the analysis with the sea ice data. The ERA5 has shown consistent spatial patterns and temporal variability and is suitable for fundamental climate applications (Yang et al., 2021).

3.4. Salinity

Salinity data was downloaded from the Arctic Ocean Physics Reanalysis using the Copernicus Marine data store (doi:10.48670/moi-00007, accessed 1/17/2023, product id: ARCTIC_MULTIYEAR_PHY_002_003). The reanalysis is based on the TOPAZ model system, which provides data from 1991 to the present. The TOPAZ system simulates both 2-dimensional ocean variables (e.g. mixed layer depth), 3-dimensional ocean physical layers (temperature, salinity, and horizontal currents), and sea ice data. The data is produced by two coupled models: the Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) and a sea ice model (Bleck, 2002; Drange and Simonsen, 1996; Hunke and Dukowicz, 1997). The data covers the Arctic and North Atlantic Oceans, with spatial resolution between 11 and 16 km. The z-axis (water depth) ranges down to 4000 m, divided into 40 hybrid layers, with most layers located near the surface. We utilized only the salinity variable from the top 40 m of the water column (17 layers) as this is the most relevant area for biota targeted in this study (Xie and Bertino, 2022).

3.5. Discharge and runoff

Solid ice discharge is estimated across flux gates for all marine-terminating glaciers that have surface speeds of $>100 \text{ m yr}^{-1}$. Discharge is calculated by multiplication of ice thickness, surface velocity (assuming no vertical shear), ice density, and the width of the gate through which the ice flows. There is a difference between the discharge estimate from (Mankoff et al., 2020) and the actual daily ice that enters a fjord because flux gates are placed ~ 5 km upstream of the terminus, meaning there is a time lag of a few months to years between the time of the discharge estimate and when that parcel of ice enters the fjord. However, the terminus signal is seasonal, and roughly matches the upstream steadier ice discharge when analyzing the annual resolution. Downstream of the flux gates there are surface mass balance (SMB) changes that are included in this product. The uncertainty associated with these SMB changes is less than the $\sim 10\%$ uncertainty of the ice discharge product, which comes primarily from unknown ice thickness. Finally, terminus changes (that is, advance and retreat of the actual ice front, downstream from the flux gate) are not considered here, but added only ~ 1000 Gt over the 1985–2022 period (Greene et al., 2024) or roughly ~ 25 Gt/year, compared to the ~ 1000 Gt/year of solid discharge plus liquid runoff.

Liquid freshwater discharge is estimated for every stream. Discharge is calculated from the MAR and RACMO regional climate model (RCMs) for both ice-sourced runoff (rain, melting snow, and melting ice from the ice domain) and land-sourced runoff (rain and melting snow on the land domain). Runoff is routed to both the ice edge and the coast using traditional assumptions of subglacial hydrologic routing within the ice

Table 1

Sea ice seasonality data: Proportion of pixels with no value compared to total pixels analyzed.

Region	Northwest	West	Southwest	Northeast	East	Southeast
Total pixels analyzed	10,062	18,447	15,781	19,092	18,576	17,888
Pixels with NaN-value	147	2177	14,713	306	4341	14,011

domain, and traditional hydrologic routing methods within the land domain (Mankoff et al., 2021). Here we combine the land and ice runoff from both RCMs and convert from daily values of m^3/s to Gt/year (assuming 1 m^3 weighs 1000 kg). Due to the long time span of the liquid discharge, we calculated three trends for liquid discharge: 1958–2020, 1958–1978, and 1979–2020 to identify possible acceleration in runoff trends.

3.6. Chlorophyll *a*

Satellite-based estimates of surface chlorophyll *a* concentrations were obtained from the Copernicus-GlobColour project, which was developed and validated by ACRI-ST, France, and made available through the E.U.

Copernicus Marine Services (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OCEANCOLOUR_GLO_BGC_L4_MY_009_104/description, accessed 10/26/2023). We used the monthly averaged fields from 1997 to 2021, as data are not available for periods prior to 1997, with a horizontal resolution of 4 km. From these, we created the summer average (April to October) concentration of chlorophyll.

The trend in satellite-based surface chlorophyll concentration was downloaded from the E.U. Copernicus Marine Services (doi:10.48670/moi-00230, accessed 11/17/2023) and based on a chlorophyll time series produced for climate-focused studies by the ESA Ocean Color Climate Change Initiative (Jackson, 2020; Sathyendranath et al., 2019). The trend calculation was based on the work by Vantrepotte and Mélin (2009). The northerly location and large latitudinal extent of the Greenlandic coastline mean that the number of data points with values from satellite-based estimates of chlorophyll is highly variable, with higher data availability in southern regions and lower in northerly regions. Further, a large difference in data availability can be attributed to the presence of ice. Under-ice blooms are now understood to be ubiquitous in the Arctic Ocean (Arrigo et al., 2012) including the sea around Greenland (Ardyna and Arrigo, 2020), and a field only including open water areas is thus likely not representative for the surface chlorophyll of the area. Another issue for satellite-based estimates of chlorophyll concentrations is the optical complexity of coastal waters, making it challenging to provide accurate estimates of chlorophyll with algorithms developed for open water conditions (Wang et al., 2005). One issue is riverine outflow of colored organic material, which may artificially increase the estimated chlorophyll concentrations (Chaves et al., 2015). Further, the ocean-color algorithms are based on assumptions regarding the vertical distribution of chlorophyll in the water column and the mixed layer depth, thus introducing new uncertainties (Carr et al., 2006). However, satellite-based estimates are a powerful tool for the understanding of large-scale chlorophyll dynamics over several years and were the best data option for the current study.

4. Results

4.1. Sea ice concentration

Sea ice was widespread in the NW, NE, W, and E Greenland, as well as along the coastline in the SE during the study period. By contrast, there was almost no sea ice in the SW (Fig. 2, Table S1). Trends of annual sea ice concentration showed a significant decrease in sea ice concentration for all regional averages except for NE (Table S2). The most substantial decrease was observed in the E ($-5.3 \text{ \% decade}^{-1}$) along the ice edge, followed by the W ($-4.2 \text{ \% decade}^{-1}$) with the strongest decline in the Qeqertarsuup Tunua area ($69^\circ\text{N}, 52^\circ\text{W}$), and the SE along the coastline ($-3 \text{ \% decade}^{-1}$). Trends were smaller in NW ($-2.1 \text{ \% decade}^{-1}$) and SW ($-1.4 \text{ \% decade}^{-1}$), reflected by a low rate of change across all individual pixels and the almost absent sea ice in the SW (Fig. 2 & table S3). Although the NE did not show an overall significant trend in sea ice concentration, its southern part (approximately 76°N – 78°N) experienced a decrease (Fig. 2). It is noteworthy that trends along the

coastline in this region were generally insignificant (Fig. 2).

The spatial distribution of decadal trends in sea ice concentration also differed markedly between seasons (Fig. S1). In spring, mean sea ice concentration ranged between 30 and 98 % within all regions except in SW (12 %) and showed significant negative trends in all regions (1.2 – $4.9 \text{ \% decade}^{-1}$) except NE. Trends were most pronounced in E, SE, W, and near the Wolstenholme fjord ($76^\circ\text{N}, 69^\circ\text{W}$) in NW. In summer, mean sea ice concentration was lower (9–34 %) except in NW and NE (69–84 %) where only Wolstenholme fjord (NW) and Kronprins Christian Land ($80^\circ\text{N}, 14^\circ\text{W}$) (NE) had a lower ice concentration. All easterly regions showed significant negative trends along the ice edge and near the coastline, the NW and the northernmost part of the W likewise. In autumn, mean sea ice concentration exceeded that of the summer in the northernmost regions but remained close to zero in SE. Autumn trends were spatially identical to summer trends, generally strongest in E. In winter, patterns were very similar to spring (Fig. S1). Hence, overall, the seasonal patterns of trends resembled the annual patterns (Fig. 2) with major losses in E, W and SE and less distinct trends in the still ice-covered North and in the largely ice-free SW.

4.2. Sea ice seasonality – melt date, freeze date, and open water period

A strong latitudinal gradient was identified in the timing of the melt date (day 8–166) and freeze date (day 254–356), with the southerly regions melting earlier and freezing later (Fig. 3, Table S1). In general, the open water period varied from 10 to 12 months in the south to approximately 3 months in the north (Fig. 3), but spatial variations were large within regions. Annual variation in seasonality appeared to differ between regions, with eastern regions, especially E and SE had more variable melt and freeze dates compared to western regions (Fig. 3), likely caused by variable export of drift ice through the Fram Strait. Significant changes in open water period were especially pronounced in E along the ice edge, in W in the Qeqertarsuup Tunua area, and along the coastline in SE (Fig. 2). In both northern regions, trends in sea ice seasonality were smaller and mainly driven by local changes. In SW there was a significant trend in the open water period. The trend was driven by changes in the 1980s and early 1990s, while there are almost no changes in recent decades (Fig. 3). In all regions, the open water period generally extended in both spring and autumn, but earlier melting is more pronounced than later freezing, especially in SW and SE.

4.3. Annual Sea surface temperature

The Greenland coastal and shelf waters were dominated by cold waters with the annual mean temperature ranging from $4.71 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the south to $-1.68 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the north. In the south there was an offshore band with warmer sea surface temperature (SST), which is linked to the Irminger current that advects warm, saline Atlantic waters into the region (Fig. 4). Significant warming trends in SST were documented in all regions, with temperature increases ranging from $0.22 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$ to $0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$ in E, W, SE, SW, and $0.01 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $0.03 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$ in the NE and NW region (Fig. 4; Supplementary Table S2).

In spring (March, April, May), SST means ranged from $-1.69 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $2.95 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with lowest temperatures in NE, NW, E, and W (Fig. 4; Table S2). Significant trends were observed for NW, W, and E, ranging from $0.006 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (NW) to $0.063 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$. In SE many pixels showed significant trends, but when averaged across the region the trend was not significant. In summer (June, July, August), mean SST ranged from $-1.68 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to $6.9 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Summer SST were especially high along the western coastline (Fig. 4). At this time of year, trends were highly significant and most marked in W ($0.69 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$), SW ($0.39 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$), E ($0.45 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$) and SE ($0.61 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$) (Fig. 4; Supplementary Table S2). Trends were particularly steep in the northern part of the W region and in the SE region. On average, SST in NW ($0.14 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$) and NE ($0.05 \text{ }^\circ\text{C decade}^{-1}$) regions also increased significantly, but with small rates of change.

Fig. 2. Mean (left column), standard deviation (std, second column), linear trends (third column) and trend significance (right column) of annual average sea ice concentration (first row), melt date (second row), freeze date (third row), and open water period (last row). Data are from the period 1979–2021.

Fig. 3. Annual mean values of melt date and freeze date for Greenland (solid black line) and all regions (dashed lines) presented as day of the year. The distance between lines of same color equals the open water period.

4.4. Salinity

The coastline around Greenland showed distinct patterns in mean annual salinity (0–40 m) (Fig. 5).

Towards NE, the salinity was generally lower (30–32 PSU). Along the west coast, the salinity also decreased towards the north. There is no uniform response in salinity trends, and they were characterized by a mottled distribution, resulting in small, but significant, negative regional trend in W ($-0.03 \text{ PSU decade}^{-1}$), while increasing in E ($0.03 \text{ PSU decade}^{-1}$), and SE ($0.04 \text{ PSU decade}^{-1}$). The trends were strongest in SE and NE, where some pixels show salinity increased by $0.25 \text{ PSU decade}^{-1}$.

4.5. Runoff

There was no latitudinal pattern in the solid ice discharge. The highest mean annual solid ice discharges during the period 1987–2022 were observed in W (149.2 Gt yr^{-1}) and SE (145.6 Gt yr^{-1}), as compared to the NE (25.48 Gt yr^{-1}) and SW (19.36 Gt yr^{-1}) (Fig. 6). Keep in mind that different regions have different flux-gate widths. Similarly, decadal trends showed a larger increase in solid discharge in W ($12.82 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$) compared to the other regions (1.26 Gt yr^{-1} to $4.60 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$). SW, characterized by few discharging glaciers, even experienced a decrease in solid ice discharge of $0.48 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$ (Table S3).

Both liquid and solid ice discharge differed across the six regions. On the west coast, the annual liquid discharge decreased markedly towards the north. The east coast exhibited a comparable pattern but with higher liquid discharge in E compared to SE (Fig. 6). The annual mean liquid discharge in all regions was higher in 1979–2020 ($43.99\text{--}119.74 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1}$) compared to 1958–1978 ($30.82\text{--}103.26 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1}$), indicating an acceleration in runoff over time. This acceleration is more apparent

when compared to both the overall decadal trends from 1958 to 1978 ($-8.67\text{--}1.4 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$) with the 1979–2020 trends ($5.54\text{--}12.11 \text{ Gt yr}^{-1} \text{ decade}^{-1}$) across regions. Between 1958 and 1978 the trends were not significant.

4.6. Z-score

The most pronounced cumulative changes in the quantified environmental drivers occurred in W, E, and SE, as reflected by summed z-scores trends ranging from 0.337 to 0.363. Significantly increasing trends in z-scores were observed in all parameters (using runoff from 1979 to 2022) within these regions. In contrast, NW exhibited lower accumulated changes (0.250), with salinity showing no significant z-score trend. The NE and SW regions displayed the least cumulative change, with summed z-score trends of 0.169 and 0.189, respectively (Fig. 7). Notably, salinity was the only parameter that did not exhibit a significant z-score trend in SW, whereas in NE, this was also the case for sea ice concentration and sea ice seasonality (Table S5).

4.7. Biological time series

In the peer-reviewed literature, we identified 43 studies which reported a total of 94 time series on biota (Fig. 8, Table S6). In three time series two responses were recorded resulting in a total of 97 responses. In seven time series, the trend represented multiple regions yielding a total count of 112 trends within different regions. 73 (78%) of the time series documented significant changes over time, with 37 of the time series associated with an environmental driver. Most commonly a single driver was identified ($n = 33$), while four studies identified significant effects of two drivers (Fig. 9). The two most frequent environmental drivers were changes in sea ice regime ($n = 20$) and temperature (incl. Sea (17) and air temperatures (2)) ($n = 19$), followed by increased runoff

Fig. 4. Mean (left column), standard deviation (std, second column), linear trends (third column) and trend significance (right column) of annual (first row), spring (second row), and summer (third row) sea surface temperature from the period 1979–2021 based on ERA5 data.

($n = 2$). Time series were unevenly distributed among regions with the highest frequency in W ($n = 37$) and SW ($n = 30$) and fewer in E ($n = 15$), NW ($n = 13$), SE ($n = 12$), and NE ($n = 5$). Adding to this, many of the studies were clustered around specific regions characterized by easy accessibility (i.e. around villages, and monitoring stations). Along the west coast, this included Nuuk ($n = 19$), Qeqertarsuup Tunua ($n = 12$), Nuussuaq ($n = 15$), and Qaanaq ($n = 10$). On the east coast, the area near Ittoqqortoormiit ($n = 5$) and Daneborg ($n = 5$) were the most studied.

Seabirds were the most studied group ($n = 48$) followed by fish ($n = 17$), marine mammals ($n = 10$), benthic flora ($n = 9$), plankton (phytoplankton and zooplankton) ($n = 8$), and benthic fauna ($n = 2$). The most common type of ecological response was changes in abundance and demography ($n = 64$), of which seabird observations constituted the majority ($n = 45$), followed by growth and condition ($n = 13$), regime shifts and community changes ($n = 15$), range shifts ($n = 4$), and behavior and phenology ($n = 1$). The direction of these trends will be evaluated alongside changes in environmental drivers in the

Fig. 5. Mean (left column), standard deviation (std, second column), linear trends (third column) and trend significance (right column) of annual salinity in the period 1991–2021 based on TOPAZ data.

discussion.

The nine benthic flora time series represented changes in growth and condition, abundance and demography, and community changes. Six of the time series documented no changes, while three (from W and SW) documented increases in either growth ($n = 1$) or relative abundance ($n = 2$) driven by changes in air temperature and open water period. Benthic fauna was the most under-represented with only two time series, both focused on growth and condition, documenting no trends although increased growth correlated with less sea ice.

The eight time series of planktonic species were distributed with four studies on phytoplankton and four on zooplankton, which both have been significantly affected by changes in run-off and sea ice cover. The four phytoplankton time series represented SW ($n = 2$), NW ($n = 1$) and NE ($n = 1$) and focused on regime shift and community changes ($n = 2$), abundance and demography ($n = 3$), growth and condition ($n = 1$). Only one time series showed a significant trend in growth and condition, abundance and demography in SW Greenland. For zooplankton, time series focused on abundance and demography ($n = 2$), regime shifts and community changes ($n = 2$) and identified shifts in these variables in W and E, respectively.

Time series of fish all represented the two southern regions (SW, SE), and primarily represented abundance and demography ($n = 6$), regime shift and community changes ($n = 7$), but also growth and condition ($n = 3$) and range shift ($n = 1$). Fourteen significant trends were identified in species richness, biomass, and abundance, all driven by changes in temperatures. Species richness and abundance generally decreased in the SE region, and increased in SW.

For seabirds, the majority of the 48 time series focused on abundance and demography ($n = 46$), while few studies looked at range shifts ($n = 4$). In two of the time series two types of responses were recorded. The studies were located in NW ($n = 28$), SW ($n = 10$), NE ($n = 5$), W ($n = 3$), SE ($n = 1$), and across regions. 44 of the time series showed significant trends, while only four did not.

The ten time series for marine mammals were located in W ($n = 5$), E ($n = 3$), SE ($n = 1$), NW ($n = 1$), and focused on polar bears (*Ursus maritimus*) ($n = 8$) and whales ($n = 2$). Response variables were abundance and demography ($n = 5$), growth and condition ($n = 3$), behavior and phenology ($n = 1$), and regime shift and community changes ($n = 1$). All trends were significant and related to sea ice cover. Polar bears were mainly affected negatively in relation to diet, distance travelled, and time spent on land. However, a subpopulation in NW experienced transient benefits. Whales were affected by warming sea temperatures

and sea ice loss resulting in regime shifts and demographic changes. This positively affected boreal cetacean species, while narwhals experienced overexploitation and reduced habitats.

4.8. Summer chlorophyll

Surface concentrations of chlorophyll *a* were highest in the NW and SW regions, relatively high in W and SE, but low in NE and E (Fig. 10, Table S1). The NW and NE regions have very little data coverage due to extensive sea ice coverage and limited daylight during winter months (Fig. 2). Trends in chlorophyll were only significant in the southern half of Greenland, generally presenting increasing trends (Fig. 10).

5. Discussion

The examination of trends in environmental drivers yielded insights into the dynamics and variability of environmental changes and biological responses along the Greenland coastline. Major regional differences in trends revealed contrasting conditions from south to north as well as further disparities between the west and east coasts. These divergences can be attributed to a combination of localized phenomena, such as the export of Arctic Ocean drift ice and changing ocean currents, and broader-scale influences including weather patterns and increasing sea temperatures (Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2023; Møller and Nielsen, 2020; Spreen et al., 2020). Together, these factors create a mosaic of conditions that shape the environmental conditions affecting ecological dynamics of the regions, which highlights the likelihood of variable changes in marine biota. Linking regional variations in environmental drivers to the biota responses unveiled spatial patterns in response to climate change, despite an incomplete picture of biota responses in regard to representation across regions and biota.

5.1. Hot spots of change in Greenland seas (W, E, SE)

From the environmental drivers included, we identified the W, E and SE regions as 'hot spots' of change based on their high accumulated Z score. In these three regions the majority (78 %) of biota time-series also showed significant changes. Changes were observed across taxonomic groups and types of responses.

Environmental trends in these regions were driven by increasing sea surface temperatures, freshwater inputs, open water period, together with decreasing sea ice concentration and variations in salinity.

Fig. 6. Liquid (black, year 1958–2020) and solid ice discharge (red, year 1979–2020) across the six regions expressed in Gt per year.

In both W and E, diminishing sea ice profoundly affected the growth, condition, abundance, and demography of marine mammals. Polar bears experienced habitat loss due to reduced sea ice cover, leading to altered migration patterns and increased time spent on land (Laidre et al., 2018). Additionally, body condition deterioration is observed across all sex-, age-, and reproductive classes, with anticipated reduction in litter sizes. In E, the seals preyed upon by polar bears included a higher proportion of sub-Arctic species in years with high air temperatures and less sea ice (McKinney et al., 2013), which could reflect climate-related changes in the health of the seals and polar bears. In W, Beluga whales (*Delphinapterus leucas*) also showed a shift in distribution as larger sea ice free areas become available earlier in the spring (Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2016). Sea temperatures were the only reported driver in SE based on the 11 time series from the literature, although our study reports multiple environmental drivers within the region. Another study does point to changes in sea ice, sea temperature, and salinity causing a regime shift in the region, where an increased number of cetacean boreal species (humpback (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), fin (*Balaenoptera physalus*), killer (*Orcinus orca*), and pilot whales (*Globicephala melas*) and white-beaked dolphins (*Lagenorhynchus albirostris*)), that are either new for the area or now occurring in historically large numbers, has occurred. Meanwhile a decrease in the catches of narwhale and walrus has co-

occurred suggesting that these species are being impacted by habitat changes and overexploitation (Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2023). Thus, it is evident that the changing sea ice and sea temperatures are altering the marine ecosystems in these regions, but information on the effect of other environmental drivers remains limited.

Despite exhibiting similar trends in drivers, zooplankton communities have responded differently to changes between regions. Trends in zooplankton, present in both W and E, were related to local, interacting physical factors. In Qeqertarsuup Tunua in W, copepod communities have shifted with the Atlantic copepods species *Calanus finmarchicus* replacing the larger Arctic and more lipid-rich species, *Calanus hyperboreus* and *C. glacialis* (Møller and Nielsen, 2020). The change in copepod composition correlated significantly with sea ice changes, but the *Calanus* species in the Qeqertarsuup Tunua, are probably more related to changes in atmosphere and ocean circulations, impacting advection of copepods (Møller and Nielsen, 2020). Conversely, a 13-year time series in the Young Sound fjord (E) revealed interannual variations but no major trends in copepod abundance, suggesting a relatively resilient copepod community (Middelbo et al., 2019). Thus, the impact of climate change on biota is influenced by a combination of local environmental factors and regional oceanographic conditions.

Fig. 7. Sum of the absolute values of the z-score trends (units of standard deviation per year) for environmental drivers across different regions, considering only significant trends. This metric represents the cumulative strength of environmental change, irrespective of the direction of individual trends.

5.2. Regions of moderate change

The Northwest and Northeast regions displayed less pronounced changes in the physical environment including sea ice, likely because of consistently low sea surface temperatures. There has however been an increase in open water period, and a decline in the presence of multiyear ice (Parkinson and Cavalieri, 2008). An analysis of 18 studies from the combined northern regions identified ten significant trends (56 %) in response to climate change of which six represented Wolstenholme Fjord, where changes in the open water period surpassed the regional average. The small number of time series in the northern regions, especially NE, makes it difficult to compare to other regions. However, overall, the consistently high sea ice concentrations were reflected in the biota responses. For example, a subpopulation of polar bears in NW Greenland is experiencing transient benefits of increased productivity due to longer open water periods, while there is still sufficient sea ice

serving as polar bear habitat. However, in the future conditions will resemble W Greenland if sea ice extent continues to decline (Laidre et al., 2020). Similarly, seabirds are generally responding positively to climate change in northern and eastern Greenland, as a longer open water period allows for earlier and easier feeding opportunities. Northwestern colonies of the sea ice dependent bird species thick-billed murre (*Uria lomvia*) and black-legged kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) are still resilient to changes, but declines are evident in other regions, partly related to human activity (harvest) (Kampp et al., 1994). The sea ice dependent seabird ivory gull (*Pagophila eburnea*) is declining in SE, while there are concerns for the little Auk (*Alle alle*) and thick-billed murre numbers in the future (Boertmann et al., 2020). The breeding success of little auk is linked to the availability and phenology of their zooplankton prey (Møller et al., 2018). A general deterioration in the North Atlantic marine environment is also expected to impact recruitment in Greenland colonies (Kampp et al., 1994; Labansen et al., 2010; Merkel et al., 2014). On the other hand, boreal seabird species are expected to increase or immigrate as observed in Svalbard (Descamps and Strøm, 2021). Lastly, time series of chlorophyll *a* and fluorescence in both the NE and NW region showed minimal changes over time. One study showed that despite increased nutrient inputs to surface water in autumn, the chlorophyll *a* concentration remained low, challenging the notion that longer ice-free seasons necessarily correlate with high autumn production (Freyria et al., 2021; Nöthig et al., 2015). Thus, overall, the literature suggests that the biota in northern regions of Greenland, despite some alterations, seems to be yet to show major changes.

The SW region showed the lowest accumulated Z score, with sea surface temperatures and liquid runoff being the predominant drivers of change. The region experienced major declines in sea ice in the 1980s and 1990s but since then, sea ice has been virtually absent outside fjord systems, suggesting that the transition to a new regime in this important driver has occurred, setting this area apart from other Greenland marine ecosystems. Ecosystem change in the SW region is therefore likely to undergo different changes in ecosystem structure and functioning, especially compared to the W and E regions, where changes in sea ice remain the key changing component. This was also reflected by sea temperatures being the only reported driver of change, with the exception of a single time series of biota change related to runoff (Oksman et al., 2022). However, 73 % of biota trends were still significant in the region. The rising sea temperatures have been linked to shifts in the depth distribution of halibut (*Reinhardtius hippoglossus*). Biomass increased at shallow (400–800 m) and intermediate (801–1200 m) depths due to migration from deep waters (1201–1500 m) to prey on an increased amount of boreal species (Lekanda et al., 2021). As a consequence, shallower water experienced a reduced biodiversity due to top-down forcing (Lekanda et al., 2021). On the other hand, halibut has become less frequent in deeper waters, which can positively affect the prey species here. This demonstrates the complex impacts of warming, and how impacts on a single species can radiate throughout marine ecosystems affecting biodiversity, abundance, and biomass.

Parallel observations are noted in SE, where fluctuations in sea temperatures correlate with changes in boreal fish abundance (Post et al., 2021). On the continental slope (400–1500 m depth), fish communities, a decrease in Arctic and Subarctic fish biomass, abundance, and species richness has been observed (Emblemsvåg et al., 2020), with boreal species, primarily mobile generalists, replacing Arctic bottom-dwelling benthivores. However, this increase is insufficient to counteract the loss of Arctic species, resulting in a decline in functional diversity, potentially reducing the system's resilience to climate change (Emblemsvåg et al., 2022). However, sea temperatures often showed interdecadal variability, so despite fulfilling the criteria to be included in our literature survey, this cannot directly be linked to climate change. Overall, the available information indicates that, in southern regions, increased sea temperatures are expected to influence fish community structure. The increasing air temperature also led to an increase in runoff from the Greenland ice sheet in SW. This has resulted in increased

Fig. 8. Distribution of biological time series (Table S6) compiled from the literature grouped by biota and type of response. The pie charts below the map represent the total distribution, while region-specific charts are shown adjacent to the respective region. The left sets of pie charts are grouped by biota and the sets right by response type. Red circles represent time series with trends, purple circles represent those without. Numbers within the circles represent the number of trends in case they overlap geographically.

Fig. 9. Distribution of environmental drivers related to changes in biota around Greenland, based on literature review. Yellow symbols represent changes in sea ice (incl. Concentration, open water period, coverage), teal/yellow symbols represent changes in both sea ice and runoff, red/yellow symbols represent changes in sea ice and air temperature, teal symbols represent changes in runoff, and purple symbols represent changes in sea temperature.

pelagic primary productivity near marine-terminating glaciers, at levels unprecedented since, at least, the late 19th century, and suggests that increased mass loss from the Greenland ice sheet continues to promote high coastal productivity (Oksman et al., 2022). However, projections suggest a transition of marine-ending glaciers onto land (Carr et al., 2013; Howat and Eddy, 2011; Meire et al., 2017), with significant implications for fjord productivity due to alterations in nutrient upwelling and increased turbidity (Juul-Pedersen et al., 2015; Meire et al., 2023). Such movements can have major impacts on ecosystems services, as land-terminating fjord systems sustain only one-third of the annual production and half the CO₂ uptake per unit area compared to marine-terminating fjord systems (Meire et al., 2023).

Runoff effects in northern regions do not yield the same outcome, underscoring the complexity of runoff impacts, which depend on the interplay with other environmental drivers such as sea ice cover and the characteristics of freshwater output.

5.3. The complexity of Greenland marine ecosystem change

Environmental drivers of biological communities are many and multiple drivers can have synergistic, antagonistic, additive, and neutral effects both within and among different biota (Boyd et al., 2018; Sage, 2020). Few of the studies that we identified examined these interactive effects. Decreasing salinities (Barrett et al., 2022) and ocean acidification (Thyrring et al., 2023) can potentially offset poleward range expansions facilitated by warming, and in the case of benthic primary producers, the interplay of drivers such as coastal erosion and increased turbidity due to runoff from land can to some extent, counteract the increased light availability related to longer open water periods (Ji and Gao, 2021; Krause-Jensen et al., 2020; Lebrun et al., 2022). Further studies on the complex interacting effects of climate change on regional to local scale combined with a wide spatial representation of ecosystems are, therefore, important to predict how the marine ecosystems along the Greenland coast will respond to climate change in the future. This is especially important in coastal ecosystems that represent the transitional zone between the ocean and land, and thus are impacted by environmental drivers from both.

Major knowledge gaps also exist related to the actual cause-and-effect coupling between individual species and the many manifestations of climate change around Greenland. The discharge of ice and meltwater from the Greenland Ice Sheet has increased significantly and contributes markedly to the cumulative Z-score especially in SE, W and

Fig. 10. Summer (April to October) chlorophyll a concentration mean (first column), standard deviation (second column), significant annual trends (third column), number of observations pixels (fourth column) from 1998 to 2021 in the six regions. The mean values are expressed in mg m⁻³, while changes are displayed as percent per year. Data was obtained from the Copernicus store.

SW Greenland. However, examples of the ecosystem effects are largely absent in our survey. Combined it means that the current capacity to reliably predict future ecosystem change is still very limited which in turn limits adaptation actions by the Greenland society which is completely reliant on its living marine resources.

The Arctic is a notoriously understudied region due to limited accessibility and expensive fieldwork. On a Pan-Arctic scale, the literature on trends in biota has increased in recent years from 53 identified trends in 2011 (Wassman et al., 2011) to 253 studies in 2023 (Deb and Bailey, 2023). On the Greenland scale, the 94 marine time series based on 43 studies included here is a strong increase from only six studies included in the 2011 review (Wassman et al., 2011). Yet Greenland marine ecosystems are poorly understudied with only few time series and long stretches of coastline without information making it difficult to interpret how the biota is responding to climate change. For example, the identified time-series here are strongly biased towards higher trophic levels (fish, birds, mammals), with lower trophic levels being scarce and ecosystem wide changes in for example biodiversity are absent. Furthermore, studies should be expanded in space and should extend several decades to eliminate interannual and decadal oscillation (Hegerl et al., 2019; Lekanda et al., 2021; Nöthig et al., 2015). Additionally, several studies identified no driver of change or alternatively a single driver was identified based on correlation type analysis. As a consequence, most studies focus on identifying bottom-up effects while top-down pathways are largely neglected (with a noteworthy exception of (Heide-Jørgensen et al., 2023)).

Although changes in Greenland biota were documented in 78 % of the available time series, an environmental driver was only identified in 34 % of these and typically only one driver was highlighted. This demonstrates that marine communities around Greenland are indeed changing, but major knowledge gaps persist in our understanding of interacting drivers. Declining sea ice cover and increasing sea surface temperatures were identified as key drivers of change. This is not surprising as they control habitat, light penetration, mixed layer depth, and metabolism. Very few studies related changes in biota to other environmental drivers, including turbidity, which we did not include due to the lack of reliable data along the coastal zone of Greenland. Gradients in environmental drivers have also been studied at spatial scale and demonstrated how marine ecosystem structure and function on several trophic levels are impacted by natural gradients in for example air temperature and sea ice cover (Krause-Jensen et al., 2012; Thyrring et al., 2021). Although these studies are not included here, they provide additional evidence that the trends in environmental drivers shown here are driving bottom-up effects on the marine ecosystem around Greenland.

6. Conclusion

Our findings demonstrate that climate change is impacting the coastal ocean around Greenland with obvious regional differences in key drivers and their pace of change. This mosaic of conditions shapes complex, region-specific environmental dynamics, leading to variable biological responses across marine ecosystems. We provide a first estimate of the cumulative change of several readily available climatic drivers and identify W, E and SE Greenland as regions experiencing accelerated change, which may indicate areas of heightened potential impact of ecological impacts. Based on a literature survey we document widespread changes in ecosystem structure and functioning in the ocean around Greenland with 78 % of included studies documenting significant change, 50 % of which are directly linked to climate-related drivers. Declining sea ice cover and rising sea temperatures consistently emerge as the dominant drivers of change. The most common biological responses to environmental changes are shifts in abundance and demography, particularly among seabirds and fish. Seabirds predominantly exhibit significant changes in these metrics, often associated with sea ice loss and warming. Fish show contrasting trends, with increases in

species richness and abundance in southwestern Greenland and declines in the southeast, primarily driven by temperature changes. Marine mammals are strongly affected by sea ice loss, with polar bears generally experiencing negative impacts, while some cetaceans benefit from warming conditions. Plankton and benthic flora/fauna display mixed responses, with relatively few significant trends, which may reflect both biological resilience and data limitations. We identified several knowledge gaps, particularly regarding the impact of multiple drivers and less frequently assessed drivers, lack of data on lower trophic levels as well as the role of biological interactions in driving changes in population and ecosystem structure. Additionally, we found a regional bias towards more easily accessible areas highlighting potential biases in spatial data coverage. Addressing these gaps will be critical for improving our understanding of climate-driven changes in Greenland's marine ecosystems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thomas Gjerluff Ager: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Mikael K. Sejr:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Carlos M. Duarte:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Kenneth D. Mankoff:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Vibe Schourup-Kristensen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **David Boertmann:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Eva Friis Møller:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Jakob Thyrring:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Dorte Krause-Jensen:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2025.179443>.

Data availability

The code used in this study is publicly available on GitHub at the following repository: <https://github.com/Tagerv1/Greenland-environmental-drivers>.

The data supporting the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11352998>, reference number <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11352998>.

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